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Risks and Benefits Associated with Superior Mobile Banking Technology

Under the Supervision of
Mohammed Moin Uddin Reza
Assistant Professor
Department of Accounting & Information Systems
Faculty of Business Studies
Bangladesh University of Professionals

Submitted By
Asma Chowdhury Luna
Roll No: 18019080, Id: 18014471
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Mohammed Moin Uddin Reza

Assistant Professor

Department of Accounting & Information Systems

Bangladesh University of Professionals

Mirpur Cantonment, Dhaka- 1216.

Subject: Submission of Dissertation on “Risks and Benefits Associated with Superior Mobile Banking Technology”.

Sir,

With due honour, I am wishing to inform you that it was a matter of great pleasure as well as learning to prepare a dissertation on “Risks and Benefits Associated with Superior Mobile Banking Technology”, actually I have enjoyed more preparing this dissertation paper. I have worked very hard to prepare this dissertation. So, I would highly oblige if the content of the dissertation has been acceptable to you.

Though I have put my best efforts yet it is very likely that the dissertation may have some mistakes and omissions that are unintentional. So, I hope that the dissertation will worthy of your consideration.

With Respect yours,

Asma Chowdhury Luna

DECLARATION

I, Asma Chowdhury Luna, a student of MBA Professionals major in Finance. I would like to solemnly declare here that the report on “Risks and Benefits Associated with Superior Mobile Banking Technology” has been authentically prepared by me. While preparing this report, I didn’t breach any copyright act intentionally.

I am further declaring that I did not submit this report anywhere for awarding any degree, diploma, or certificate.

Asma Chowdhury Luna
ID:18019080
Batch:19; Major: Finance
Program: MBA Professionals

Mohammed Moin Uddin Reza
Assistant Professor
Department of Accounting & Information Systems
Bangladesh University of Professionals

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A report that requires a lot of information from various corners is not the works of its authors or prepare-rs only. To prepare a report by collecting data of many kinds, one is to depend upon many people and much other information.

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ABSTRACT

The important goal of this study is to examine the way to increase the range of mobile banking users in Bangladesh which is based on the problem statement and other issues that affect customers' uses of mobile banking. The study also investigates the factors, demographic variables, and user's perceptions that influence the adoption of mobile banking in Bangladesh. The study describes mobile banking usage based on age, gender, education level, working status, income level, geographic location of the respondents, possession of the mobile phone and bank account as demographic variable and the perception of users in terms of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, perceived risk, awareness, customer service, overall customer intention. A questionnaire has been made to conduct a survey on a sample of 120 mobile banking users (active and inactive) and non-users. The evaluation revealed that maximum involved respondent is male and office workers age 18-30years. Correlation and regression analysis of this study has found that the Usage of mobile banking service and perceived risk has a negative correlation. On the other hand, there is also a negative relationship between Customer trust and perceived risk. This study also revealed that in order to expand mobile banking adoption intention, banks have to build favourable attitude through enhanced perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, consumer awareness as well as perceived risks associated.

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *Background of the Study*

Day to day our world is turning into technology-based and we have become dependent on it. The mobile phone is one of the gifts of science and technology. Nowadays we use this device in our personal life as well as professional life. Among the various benefits of mobile phone most highlighted benefit is mobile banking.

Mobile banking is a service which enables customers to perform their banking task on mobile phone with the help of the internet from anywhere to everywhere such as view account balance, make instant fund transfers and pay bills, transfers such as social welfare payments and pensions, study recent transaction, block ATM card, etc. One of the first commercial applications of mobile commerce was mobile banking(m-banking) (Barnrs & Corbitt, 2003; Ven-katesh & Davis, 1996). It started in Bangladesh on 31st March 2011 which is launched by Dutch Bangla Bank Ltd. Brac Bank is in the second position who has undertaken these services to reach their customers. After that, all the other banks in Bangladesh open mobile banking. Since the number of mobile phone users is increasing day by day, On the same time purchasing products & services using mobile phones and other mobile devices are also increasing. Besides, the use of mobile banking is still in the initial stages and more research in this field is desirable (Barati & Mohammadi, 2009).

It is a very much sensitive service because it deals with money. It is a 24hours service. Some mobile banking service providers are Rocket, Bkash, Ucash, Mycash, Mcash etc. Among those Bkash is becoming the market leader by holding more than half of the market. Internet banking and mobile banking (m-banking) have become the self-directed service delivery channel that allows banks to endow with information and recommend services to their customers with more expediency via the web services technology (Mohammad Masudul Hassan, Airin Rahman, Sharmin Afrin, Md. Gulam Rabbany, 2014).

Mobile banking provides a lot of benefits but also rises some risk. It makes the banking system easier and cost-effective for the customer. Currently, there are 16 banks that are involved in providing mobile financial services (Bangladesh post,04 Dec2019). Many banks and financial institutions reach a large no. of customers on a low unit cost basis. Now people no need to go to the bank and wait in line for their serial number for performing their banking tasks. A person can perform those activities anywhere through mobile phones within a short time. Electricity bills, gas bills, water bills, purchasing, even paying monthly salary can be paid with the mobile banking system. Some vendors are providing services for sending foreign remittances through mobile banking.

Besides benefits, there are also some risks associated with mobile banking. Occasionally users receive some fake bank SMS and calls. If the phone is misplaced then there may be a risk that criminals can get access to the mobile banking PIN and different sensitive information. All regions do not have internet access and all mobile phone do not support the internet. Only smartphone users can get those services so its limitation is a whopping issue to the customers.

“As the way of money transaction through mobile banking is easier compared to the conventional banking process, the number of mobile banking subscribers in Bangladesh has noticeably increased over the past years in Bangladesh. But most of the subscribers are not involved in the transaction and which is why the numbers of inactive subscribers have been increasing, an updated report of the Mobile Financial Services of Bangladesh Bank said. As of October 2019, there are 7 crore 73 lakh and 95 thousand subscribers of mobile banking in Bangladesh. Among them, only 2 crore 90lakh and 11 thousand are active subscribers. The remaining 4crore 83lakh and 83thousand subscribers are totally inactive”. (Bangladesh post, 04 Dec 2019)

Based on the risks and benefits of mobile banking, this study focused on several factors why the numbers of inactive subscribers of mobile banking have been increasing so that MFIs can improve their facilities and make people aware of the development of the banking sector in Bangladesh. These factors are age, generation, Standard of living, geographic location, profession, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, perceived risks, awareness, availability of the smartphone, internet access, etc.

Mobile banking is a blessing both for the bank and the customers, that's why it is both ways game. It creates a better future for the banking business in Bangladesh.

• *Problem Statement*

Today most of the banks in Bangladesh and Financial institutions are providing a wide range of mobile banking services under one roof. Mobile banking users over the past years increased in Bangladesh but most of the subscribers are not involved in transactions that's why inactive subscriber has been increasing. However, it is yet a matter of investigation to why inactive subscriber has been increasing. Therefore, the current study will try to find out why customers are not using mobile banking.

- *Objectives of the Research*

The overall objective of the research is to analyze how to increase the number of mobile banking users in Bangladesh which is based on the problem statement and other issues that affect customers' uses of mobile banking. In determining this, the research focuses on-

- ✓ Ascertain the factors that influence the decision to use mobile banking
- ✓ Investigate the adoption of mobile banking in the Bangladeshi context
- ✓ Understand the mobile banking services that are more familiar to the Bangladeshi people
- ✓ Understand the perception of mobile banking users in Bangladesh
- ✓ Identify the factors which increase the usage of mobile banking
- ✓ Understand those factors among the selected populations
- ✓ Finally, to make some recommendations and conclusion to further the development of customer adoption of mobile banking services in Bangladesh.

- *Limitations of the Study*

In this study, there is no proper written rules and procedures could be maintained. Therefore, we have to note down what Bangladesh Bank is doing in their regular operation and few assumptions have been made based on information gathered by secondary data collection and evaluation. As a result, there might be scopes for personal error.

I faced certain limitations regarding the study which are summarized below:

- ✓ Deficiencies in proper data required for the study.
- ✓ Relevant research papers and documents were not accessible due to paid services.
- ✓ Much technical information was not available.
- ✓ A lot of procedural matters were written from their observation, which may also vary from person to person.
- ✓ The provided timeline for conducting the study is short,

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Literature Review*

The literature review indicates some studies papers which might be carried out on mobile technology. Maximum studies have been conducted in developing countries. The structure of the literature review is designed to depict the concept of mobile banking worldwide and mobile banking in Bangladesh. It goes on the areas like problems and prospects of mobile banking, factors influencing the adoption of mobile banking using a related theory of technology acceptance model. The banking sector has frequently passed through modifications in technology, customer preferences, opposition regulatory requirements, converting demographics, and social trends (Pool, Kazemi, Amani & Lashaki, 2016). Whereas mobile phone creates a possibility for the customers to carry out the banking-associated activities. According to the Bangladesh Telecommunication regulatory commission (BTRC) report, the range of mobile phone users is increasing, with over 61% of the population in Bangladesh using them.

Mobile Banking is an application of m-commerce that allows clients to get right of entry to bank accounts through mobile devices to conduct and complete bank-associated transactions consisting of balancing cheques, checking account status, money transfer, and shares selling (Kim Et al. 2009). Luo et. Al (2010), described mobile banking as a modern system for getting access to banking services through a channel wherein the clients have interaction with a bank using mobile devices.

There are such a lot of researchers who researched the factors influencing the adoption of mobile banking. Mohammad Rokibul Kabir in 2013 determined that perceived risks (anticipate social hazard), trust, convenience, and comparative advantages are the factors affecting the behavioral intention of mobile users to undertake mobile banking services in Bangladesh. His observe might have supplied better application if he considers the social hazard also. Because there may be a few social hazard arises from mobile banking and it negatively affects the adoption of mobile banking.

(Farhana Yasmin Liza, 2014) examined that perceived risk had no significant impact on the adoption of mobile banking while in recent times people are more concerned about their security/privacy. Security is getting the primary precedence of the customer. One of the biggest risks involved in online/mobile banking is the undesirable disclosure of personal information (Fang, Chan, Brzezinski, & Xu, 2005). Perceptions of risks are a powerful explanatory factor in consumer behavior as individuals appear to be more motivated to avoid mistakes than to maximize purchasing benefits (Mitchell & Groatorex, 1993). People are also concern about the performance of mobile banking because it is dealing with money which is very sensitive. The assumed risk associated with mobile/online transactions may reduce perceptions of behavioral and environmental control, and this lack of proper control is likely to negatively influence e-commerce usage intentions of customers (Zhou, 2011).

(Mohammad Majedul Islam and Md. Enayet Hossain, 2015) found that ease of use, perceived usefulness, and customer service have less impact on the adoption of mobile banking. But according to (Davis, 1989), “The perceived usefulness is the extent to which a person believes that using a particular system will enhance his or her performance, while perceived ease of use is the extent to which a person believes that using a particular system will be free of effort”. Prior research has empirically found a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness as critical factors in the use of e-banking (Chau, 2001; Mitchell, 1999; Hendrickson, & Deng, 1998; Wang, Wang Lin, & Tang, 2003). people always prefer high ease of use and usefulness from the service. Customers never compromise with the service, so it can be a major concern. So, their study would have added more value if they consider those factors.

Sharma and Kansal (2012) found that complications in functionality and privacy-related issues which is the reason why customers feel doubtful about the convenience and security of using mobile banking services. On the other hand, banks cannot provide upgraded service and technology to fulfill the needs of customers because of excessive cost and competitiveness.

One another paper which is a study by Laforet and Li (2005), focused on the relationship between consumer attitudes towards mobile banking and their adoption of mobile banking in China. They found that the only difference between users and non-users of mobile banking was concern about the confidentiality and security of the technology, primarily concerns about hackers gaining access to their information or being the victim of fraud. The study concludes that attitudes towards security and perception of risk are one of the major complex factors of discouraging adoption. Consumers have to place their trust in the mobile banking system and must be willing to take on risk. These requirements may cause the difference between users and non-users of mobile banking. Confidentiality and security of the technology can not be the only difference between the users and non-users. There are some other factors such as gender, race, type of employment, income, age, height, which have an effect on an individual's willingness to take on risk.

Nandhi (2012) found that customer ability to save is increasing with higher safe mobile banking service compared to keeping cash on hand, avoiding expense and convenience. He also found that it is a more secure mode of saving for low-income people compared to keeping cash at home. Mohammad Rokibul Kabir (2013) said that the use of mobile banking can turn basic financial services more accessible to low-income marginal people, minimizing time and distance to the nearest retail bank branches (CGAP 2006).

Goyal et al (2012) found that sex is the only demographic factor that influences the use of mobile banking service whereas the male is more interested than female. But there are some other demographic factors among them sex is one factor. Other demographic factors are age, gender, education level, working status, income level, geographic location of the respondents, possession of the mobile phone and bank account, etc.

There are a few studies conducted in Bangladesh on mobile banking which focused on the usage, problems, and prospects of mobile banking. Some are lacking in the area such as customer satisfaction, growth, and influencing factors over mobile banking usage. Alam et al (2013) give his opinion on the cost, benefits, and usage of mobile banking.

Rahman (2013) made a research on the Implementation of Mobile Banking in Bangladesh: Opportunities and challenges and found that the maximum number of users use mobile banking for checking balance options and fund transfer, fund withdrawal and mobile balance recharge, etc. But their study would have added more value if they consider that some other usage such as, get account balance update, to pay utility bills, to buy goods or services, and to buy goods and services.

Islam (2013) has conducted a study on “Mobile Banking: An Emerging Issue in Bangladesh: and found that mobile banking is saving a lot of time for the users and is also cost-efficient compared to traditional banking services. But in my study, I found that in terms of cost efficiency maximum respondent opinion is neutral neither agree nor disagree.

Wu and Wang (2005) found that cost had a minimal significant impact on the adoption of mobile banking while perceived risk, compatibility, and perceived usefulness have significant influences. Karnani (2009) argues on the same issue that Cost plays a significant role in choosing mobile banking.

Cheah et.al (2011) found that factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, relative advantage, and personal innovativeness were found positively related to the customers' intention to adopt mobile banking services. Whereas social norms were the only insignificant factor. So, the study would have added more value if they would have considered the perceived risk factor because it is negatively related to the intention of the adoption of mobile banking services.

Mattila (2010) has identified that the most important factor in encouraging the use of mobile banking services was connected to the costs of operating banking services where the mean is 4.38, a Standard Deviation of 2.15. In my study, it is in the last rank position which has an average mean of 3.98 Standard Deviation 1.13747.

While an important characteristic of any adaptation of innovative services or products similar to mobile banking is to create a proper and long-lasting awareness channel among the consumers about the service/product (Sathye, 1999). According to Sathye, (1999), the use of online banking services is fairly a new experience for a lot of people, while low awareness and knowledge of online banking is a major factor in causing people not to adopt online banking.

In this research, there I focus on many factors that directly have an impact on the adoption of mobile banking. Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, social influence, awareness, availability of the smartphone, customer service, demographic characteristics such as age, gender, education level, working status, income level, geographic location of the respondents, possession of the mobile phone and bank account has a direct impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking. Whereas perceived risks such as performance risk, security risk, time risk, social risk, Financial risk in mobile banking have a negative impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking. By considering the combination of all in one factor in this study, I believe that this research will provide a better application.

Though much of the literatures are not found related to mobile banking in Bangladesh, this paper can remove the research gap on this topic. Thus, based on the above literature this paper tries to identify the major factors influencing the adoption of Mobile Banking in Bangladesh.

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Method & Methodology

The investigation aim is to identify whether the independent variables are statistically significant factors in the adoption of mobile banking. In this research, I try to establish the effect of independent variables, perception of mobile banking users and its usefulness, perceived ease of use on independent variables, the adoption of mobile banking. Thus, I used the questionnaire as a data collection instrument. There are two types of methods in research design which are qualitative research and quantitative research. In this research, I followed the quantitative research methodology. It was used to provide numerical measurement and analysis of the adoption dynamic. I used a questionnaire for standardization to allow the collection of the results and hypothesis testing.

➤ Sources of Information

• Primary Data

Primary data is the main source of information for this research paper which I collected by fieldwork. Primary data is collected from the subscriber and non-subscribe of mobile banking.

• Secondary Data

I collect Secondary data from various books, newspapers, websites, and magazines.

Fig 1 Classification of Variable

➤ Population and Sample Size

In this research theoretical population will be all the people in Bangladesh (subscribers and non-subscribers of mobile banking). If we want to find an accurate estimate of the relationships between variables, descriptive analysis needs a sample of hundreds or even thousands of subjects such as an experiment, a survey, etc. If we select a high participation rate as a sample from the population, then the survey will less be biased. So, for my research purpose, I considered a sample size of 120 people in order to have the whole country be represented.

➤ Sampling Method

From the various sampling method, here I choose the method of random sampling for my research. Considering this method, I take respondents' responses from those samples which are essays to get access.

➤ Hypothesis

Since the adoption is the acceptance and continued use of a product, service, or idea. According to Rogers & Shoemaker (1971); Sathye (1999), consumers go through “a process of knowledge, permission, decision, and confirmation” before they are ready to adopt a product or service. The adoption or rejection of innovation begins when “the consumer becomes aware of the product”. Consumers will seek out services that offer the best value for money. So, it is necessary that mobile banking services should be available for consumer awareness and it must add value to the customers. So, by keeping this in my mind, I focus on some factors in my research and hypothesize:

- H1. The perceived usefulness of mobile banking has a positive impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H2. Perceived ease of use of mobile banking has a positive impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H3. Perceived innovation in mobile banking has a positive impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H4. Perceived risks such as performance risk, security risk, time risk, social risk, Financial risk in mobile banking have a negative impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H5. Social influence positively affects behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H6. Awareness has a positive impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking
- H7. The availability of smartphones has a positive impact on the behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H8. Demographic characteristics such as age, gender, education level, working status, income level, geographic location of the respondents, possession of a mobile phone, and bank account have a direct impact on the customer behavioral intention to use mobile banking.
- H9. Customer service positively affects the behavioral intention to use mobile banking

➤ *Proposed Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Position*

Fig 2 Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Position

➤ *Statistical Tools*

Some statistical tools were used by the researcher to carry out the study only in percentage analysis and hypothesis analysis. My research paper is based on quantitative analysis which uses numerical data to identify statistical relationships between variables. So quantitative data are numerical which I collect from the survey, questionnaires, and evaluations that include multiple-choice items and ratings. I have shown correlation and multiple regression techniques to trace casual relationships between several constructs.

➤ *Reference of Previous Research Works*

By analyzing some other writer research papers, I find that my research work is similar to the research work named “Factors Influencing the Adoption of Mobile Banking Services in Bangladesh: An Empirical Analysis” which was conducted by Mohammad Masudul Hassan, Airin Rahman, Sharmin Afrin, Md. Gulam Rabbany back in 2014. I have used correlation and regression techniques as statistical tools which are also identical to their research paper. They found five factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, subjective norm, consumer awareness, and perceived risks which is affecting the behavioral intention of mobile users to adopt mobile banking services in Bangladesh. My research paper is also working to find the same observation but I also added some other factors such as perceived innovation, social influence, Availability of smartphone, Demographic characteristics, and customer service for better decision making.

CHAPTER FOUR THE PRESENT CONDITION OF MOBILE BANKING IN BANGLADESH

➤ *The Present Condition of Mobile Banking in Bangladesh*

Now a day’s transaction through mobile banking service has been increasing day by day and the growth rate is 20% every month. The development of mobile phone users' density in Bangladesh, with an estimated 120.7 million (BTRC, October 2016) subscribers, that gives a unique opportunity to leverage and utilize the mobile banking platform to obtain the objectives and overcome the challenges of financial inclusion. In the last few years the Government, especially Bangladesh Bank, took deliberate decisions and efforts for including the large number of unbanked and under-banked people living in remote areas in abject poverty conditions all around the country.

Mobile Phone Subscribers (Millions)

Source: BTRC (2011-Oct, 2016)

Fig 3 Mobile Phone Subscriber

Central Bank permits a total of 25 banks to perform mobile banking services (Anon,2016). Whereas Dutch Bangla Bank is in the first position for introducing mobile banking. DBBL giving mobile banking services through Banglalink and Citycell. A person can open an account by visiting any of the approved agents. For this, he/she need to show proper documents with a fee of TK10. A subscriber can perform his/her banking activities through mobile phones with the help of a 4digit mobile banking PIN code. In this way, mobile banking ensures the security and safety of the user. A subscriber can deposit and withdraw cash with the help of the agent. But there is some limitation such as a subscriber can withdraw and subscribe cash five times a day and can deposit or withdraw 5000Tk per day. For transaction cash of cash out charge will be 2% which means 10Tk.

It is being familiar to many western countries. But there are some sectors which in not adopting mobile banking yet. M-commerce sectors in Bangladesh are able to provide banking services by only sending an SMS to the bank server from anywhere within a second. The proposed system is divided into five major phases/stages, the modules are - interfacing module, SMS technology adoption module, SMS banking registration module, service generation module, and data failover module. The system facilitates bank customers by providing four major services like balance inquiry, balance transfer between authenticated customers, Bank DPS payment, and bill payment without traveling to the bank physically and thus saves their precious time. At least, after evaluating each module of this developed system a satisfactory accuracy rate of 93.18 % is obtained.

Then BRAC Bank is in the second position of introducing mobile banking. For mobile banking transactions, BRAC Bank and US-based Money in Motion Introduce Bkash as a joint venture. Any national ID cardholder can open and use a Bkash account. Bkash makes transactions easy, reliable, trustworthy, and convenient. “Bkash will fundamentally change the way people now do transactions, as all transactions will be possible through mobile phones in future,” said Syed Mahbubur Rahman, managing director of the bank. “Customers will not need to come to the bank; rather the bank will go to them,” he said at a press conference in Dhaka on the occasion of its 10th founding anniversary. Bkash acts as a digital mobile wallet and anybody from anywhere at any time can take the service. “Your mobile phone will become your wallet. Customers can get financial services through phones, even by the handset that costs the lowest,” Rahman said. Bkash is now performing its operation in 4501 Union Parishads in Bangladesh. Nowadays around 7.5crore people have a digital wallet, said Mamdudur Rashid, deputy managing director of the bank. “Being the youngest Bangladeshi bank, we have emerged as the largest SME bank serving about 3.65 lakh entrepreneurs at the grassroots level, an achievement that helped global recognition for this Bangladeshi bank,” said Rashid. The bank believes in 3P philosophy, which is - people, planet, and profit, and has been active in Green banking. As a result, it has already turned 22 of its SME Unit Offices into solar-powered and targeted to convert the rest similarly by 2012.

CHAPTER FIVE DATA ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

A. *Data Analysis & Findings*

➤ *Demographic Analysis of the Respondents*

Table 1 Gender of the Respondent

Gender	Number	Percentage (%)
Male	75	62.5
Female	45	37.5
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Median	60	
Standard Deviation	21.213	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

What is your gender?

120 responses

Fig 4 Gender of the Respondent

From the above frequency table, we can see that Male respondents are more interested than female respondents. Here the total respondents are 120. Among them 75 respondents are male and 45 respondents are female. That's why the percentage of male respondents is more which is 62.5% than the female which is 37.5% in my survey. The mean of the respondent's gender is 60, Median 60 and the standard deviation is 21.213.

Table 2 Age of the Respondent

Age	Number	Percentage (%)
18-30years	105	87.5
31-40years	10	8.3
41-50years	3	2.5
More than 50years	2	1.7
Total	120	100
Mean	30	
Median	6.5	
Std. deviation	50.13	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

How old are you?
120 responses

Fig 5 Age of the Respondent

From the above frequency table, we can see that the 18-30 years respondents are more interested in mobile banking. Whereas older respondent shows less interest. The percentage of 18-30years older respondent is 87.5%, 31-40years older respondent is 8.3%, 41-50years older respondent is 2.5% and more than 50years older respondent is 1.7%. The mean of the respondent age is 30, the Median of the respondent is 6.5 and the standard deviation is 50.13.

Table 3 Occupation of the Respondent

Occupation	Number	Percentage (%)
Office workers	52	43.3
Students	46	38.3
Businessmen	11	9.2
Others	11	9.2
Total	120	100
Mean	30	
Median	28.5	
Mode	11	
Std. deviation	22.076	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Which one is your occupation?
120 responses

Fig 6 Occupation of the Respondent

From the above frequency table, we can see that the office workers and students are more interested in mobile banking. For this reason, the percentage of office workers and students is more which is 43.3% and 38.3%. On the other hand, the percentage of businessman and others are 9.2%. The mean of the respondent is 30, the mode is 11 and the standard deviation is 22.076.

Table 4 Monthly Income of the Respondent

Monthly Income	Number	Percentage (%)
0-5000Tk	25	20.8
5000-15000Tk	39	32.5
15000-30000Tk	33	27.5
Above 30000Tk	23	19.2
Total	120	100
Mean	30	
Median	29	
Std. deviation	7.394	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

How much you earn in a month?

120 responses

Fig 7 Monthly income of the Respondent

The frequency table shows that the persons who earn 5000 to 15000Tk monthly are more interested in mobile banking. For that reason, 5000 to 15000tk monthly earning respondent’s percentage which is 32.5% are more than the other respondent. Then 15000 to 30000Tk monthly earning respondents are in the second position which is 27.5% than other monthly earning respondents. Mean is 30, Median is 29 and the standard deviation is 7.394 of the Respondent’s monthly income.

Table 5 Education Status of the Respondent

Education Status	Number	Percentage (%)
Up to S.S.C	4	3.3
H.S.C	6	5
Honors	45	37.5
Above Honors	65	54.2
Total	120	100
Mean	30	
Median	25.5	
Std. deviation	30.011	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

What's your educational status?

120 responses

Fig 8 Education Status of the Respondent

The above frequency table represents that the persons who completed the above Honors level are more interested in mobile banking than the other students. For that reason, the percentage of above Honors respondents which is 54.2% are in top ranking and Honors level respondents which are 37.5% are in the second position. On the other hand, the percentage of the respondent of up to S.S.C is 3.3% and H.S.C is 5% which is very low. Mean is 30, Median is 25.5, Standard deviation is 30.011 of the respondent’s educational status.

Table 6 Marital Status of the Respondent

Marital Status	Number	Percentage (%)
Married	48	40
Unmarried	72	60
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Median	60	
Std. deviation	16.971	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

What's your Marital Status?

120 responses

Fig 9 Marital status of the Respondent

From the figure, we found that the number of unmarried respondents than married respondents are more in terms of mobile banking. So, the percentage of unmarried respondents which is 60% is more than the percentage of married respondents which is 40%. Mean is 60, Median is 60 and the standard deviation is 16.971 of the respondent’s marital status.

Table 7 Location of the Respondent

Location	Number	Percentage (%)
Dhaka	101	84.2
Comilla	4	3.3
Rangpur	2	1.7
Barisal	2	1.7
Mymensingh	1	0.8
Rajshahi	2	1.7
Sylhet	1	0.8
Chittagong	7	5.8
Total	120	100
Mean	15	
Median	2	
Mode	2	
Std. deviation	34.806	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Where do you live in?

120 responses

Fig 10 Location of the Respondent

If we focus on the location of the respondent, we will find that people of Dhaka are more interested in mobile banking than the other area’s people. For that reason, the percentage of the respondent in Dhaka is 84.2% which is a huge amount than the other area’s people. Mean is 15, Median is 2, the mode is 2 and the standard deviation is 34.806 of the respondent’s location.

Table 8 Availability of smartphone

Do you have Smartphone?	Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	116	96.7
No	4	3.3
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Mode	60	
Std. deviation	79.196	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Do you have smartphone?

120 responses

Fig 11 Availability of smartphone

If we focus on the respondents, we will see that 96,7% of respondents are having a smartphone whereas 3.3% of respondents do not have a smartphone. For that reason, we can clearly say that having a smartphone influenced the adoption of mobile banking greatly. The mean of the respondent’s availability of the smartphone is 60, the mode is 60 and the standard deviation is 79.196.

Table 9 Availability of bank account

Do you have a Bank account?	Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	105	87.5
No	15	12.5
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Median	60	
Std. deviation	63.640	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Do you have bank account?
120 responses

Fig 12 Availability of bank account

If we focus on the respondents, we will see that 87.5% of respondents are having bank account whereas 12.5% of respondents do not have a bank account. For that reason, we can clearly say that having a bank account influenced the adoption of mobile banking greatly. Because a bank account holder is more interested in mobile banking than the non-account holder. The mean of the respondent’s availability of bank account is 60, the median is 60 and the standard deviation is 63.640.

➤ *Descriptive Analysis of the Respondent*

Table 10.1 Do you use Mobile Banking?

Do you use mobile banking?	Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	105	87.5
No	15	12.5
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Median	60	
Std. deviation	63.640	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Do you use mobile banking?
120 responses

Fig 13 Usage of Mobile Banking

If we focus on the respondents, we will see that 87.5% of respondents are using mobile banking whereas 12.5% of respondents do not use mobile banking which is in a few ranges. For that reason, we can clearly say that using mobile banking influenced the adoption of mobile banking greatly. Because mobile banking holder is more interested in mobile banking than the non-mobile banking holder. Mean of the using mobile banking is 60, the median is 60 and the standard deviation is 63.640.

Table 10.2 What are the Mobile Banking Services you use?

(b)What are the mobile banking services you use?	Number	Percentage (%)
To get account balance update	11	9.2
To transfer money	21	17.5
To pay utility bills	5	4.2
To buy goods or services	4	3.3
Mobile recharge	1	0.8
To get account balance check and to buy goods and services	1	0.8
All of the above	74	61.7
None	3	2.5
Total	120	100
Mean	15	
Median	4.5	
Mode	1	
Std. deviation	24.756	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

If we focus on the mobile banking services that are used by the respondents, we will notice that a maximum number of respondents use mobile banking to get account balance update, to transfer money, to pay utility bills, to buy goods or services, mobile recharge, to get account balance check and to buy goods and services. That means all of the above services are used by the maximum percentage of respondents which is 61.7%. On the other hand, there is only a 2.5% respondent who does not use any mobile banking services. As a result, we can say that the use of mobile banking is increasing day by day. The mean of the mobile banking service use is 15, median 4.5, mode 1, and standard deviation 24.756.

Table 10.3 Perceived Usefulness

(c)Perception Statements in the Perceived Usefulness dimension	No. of the Respondent	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile banking gives flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day	120	1	5	4.43	0.77419
Mobile banking transactions save more time	120	2	5	4.61	0.66479
Mobile banking helps me to know the state of my account faster	120	1	5	4.41	0.88399
I find mobile banking cost effective as compare to visiting banks	120	1	5	3.98	1.13747
Valid number of the respondent (list wise)	120				
Average Mean	4.36				

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Table-10C shows that the mean of “Mobile banking gives the flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day” is 4.43 and the standard deviation is 0.77419, the mean of “Mobile banking transactions save more time” is 4.61 and the standard deviation is 0.66479, mean of “Mobile banking helps me to know the state of my account faster” is 4.41 and the standard deviation is 0.88399, mean of “I find mobile banking cost-effective as compare to visiting banks” is 3.98 and the standard deviation is 1.13747. As a result, the average mean value of the perception statements in the perceived usefulness dimension is 4.36 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that Perceived usefulness has a positive effect on the intention to adopt and use mobile banking. So, hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Table 11 Perceived Ease of use

Perception Statements in the Ease of use dimension	No. of the Respondent	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Learning to use Mobile banking was easy for me	120	2	5	4.39	0.79172
Instruction in the Mobile banking system are clear and understandable	120	1	5	4.06	0.89156
Mobile banking makes it easier for me to do my banking activities	120	1	5	4.43	0.79560

Valid number of the respondent (listwise)	120				
Average Mean	4.29				

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Table-11 shows that the mean of “Learning to use Mobile banking was easy for me” is 4.39 and the standard deviation is 0.79172, the mean of “Instruction in the Mobile banking system are clear and understandable” is 4.06 and the standard deviation is 0.89156, mean of “Mobile banking makes it easier for me to do my banking activities” is 4.43 and the standard deviation is 0.79560 and total valid number of the respondent (listwise) is 120. As a result, the average mean value of the perception statements in the Ease of use dimension is 4.29 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on the intention to adopt and use mobile banking. So, hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Table 12 Perceived Innovation

Perception Statements in the innovation dimension	No. of the Respondent	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I am comfortable using new technologies like mobile banking	120	1	5	4.35	0.90424
Valid number of the respondent (listwise)	120				
Average Mean	4.35				

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Table-12 shows that meaning of “I am comfortable using new technologies like mobile banking” is 4.35 and the standard deviation is 0.90424. As a result, the average mean value of the perception statements in the innovation dimension is 4.35 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that Perceived innovation has a positive effect on the intention to adopt and use mobile banking. So, hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Table 13 Perceived of Risk

Perception Statements in the Perceived of risk dimension	No. of the Respondent	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mobile banking has the chance of data loss and fraud	120	1	5	3.56	1.17248
Mobile banking has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability	120	1	3	3.29	1.02405
Valid number of the respondent (listwise)	120				
Average Mean	3.43				

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Table-13 shows that the mean of “Mobile banking has the chance of data loss and fraud” is 3.56 and the standard deviation is 1.17248, the mean of “Mobile banking has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability” is 3.29 and the standard deviation is 1.02405. As a result, the average mean value of the perception statements in the perceived risk dimension is 3.43 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that customer is neutral with the Perceived risk associated with mobile banking on the intention to adopt and use mobile banking.

Table 14.1 Are you Aware of Mobile Banking?

(a)Are you aware of mobile banking?	Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	110	91.7
No	10	8.3
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Median	60	
Std. deviation	70.711	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Are you aware of mobile banking?

120 responses

Fig 14 Awareness

This frequency table shows that 91.7% of respondents are aware of mobile banking whereas the rest of 8.3% of respondents do not have knowledge about mobile banking. The mean of awareness is 60, the median is 60 and the standard deviation is 70.711. If a respondent does not know about it then how they will motivate to use it. So, for increasing the mobile banking adoption rate, we need to aware people of the functions and benefits of mobile banking.

Table 14.2 Awareness

(b) Perception Statements in the awareness dimension	No. of the Respondent	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I think that I have received enough information about Mobile Banking	120	1	5	3.79	0.94287
I think that using the new Mobile banking service is beneficial for me	120	1	5	4.10	0.95618
Mobile banking is compatible to banking needs	120	1	5	3.94	0.95527
I use all the mobile banking services	120	1	5	3.15	1.36984
Valid number of the respondent (listwise)	120				
Average Mean	3.75				

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Table-14B shows that the meaning of “I think that I have received enough information about Mobile Banking” is 3.79 and the standard deviation is 0.94287, the mean of “I think that using the new Mobile Banking service is beneficial for me” is 4.10 and the standard deviation is 0.95618, mean of “Mobile banking is compatible to banking needs” is 3.94 and the standard deviation is 0.95527, mean of “I use all the mobile banking services” is 3.15 and the standard deviation is 1.136984. As a result, the average mean value of the perception statements in the awareness dimension is 3,75 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that customer is neutral with the Perceived awareness associated with mobile banking on the intention to adopt and use mobile banking.

Table 15 Customer Service

Perception Statements in the customer service dimension	No. of the Respondent	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Customer satisfaction of using Mobile Banking services	120	1	5	3.91	0.88873
I believe that mobile banking is trustworthy	120	1	5	3.93	0.95527
Valid number of the respondent (listwise)	120				
Average Mean				3.92	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Table-15 shows that the mean of “Customer satisfaction of using Mobile Banking services” is 3.91 and the standard deviation is 0.88873, the mean of “I believe that mobile banking is trustworthy” is 3.93 and the standard deviation is 0.95527. As a result, the average mean value of the perception statements in the customer service dimension is 3.92 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that customer is neutral with the customer service associated with mobile banking on the intention to adopt and use mobile banking.

Table 16.1 Have you Recommended Mobile Banking to others?

(a)Have you recommended mobile banking to others?	Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	107	89.2
No	13	10.8
Total	120	100
Mean	60	
Median	60	
Std. deviation	66.468	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

Have you recommended mobile banking to others?

120 responses

Fig 15 Recommendation of mobile banking

If we focus on the respondents, we will see that 89.2% of respondents are recommended mobile banking to others whereas 10.8% of respondents are not recommended mobile banking to others. That means a maximum number of respondents recommended mobile banking to others. The mean and mode of the social influence are 60 and the standard deviation is 66.468.

Table 16.2 Social influence

(b)How did you get to know about mobile banking?	Number	Percentage (%)
Internet	57	47.5
Friend	27	22.5
Bank itself	26	21.7
Newspaper	5	4.2
Family	1	0.8
Television	1	0.8
Social Media	1	0.8
Sister	1	0.8
Promotion, marketing	1	0.8
Total	120	100
Mean	13.33	
Median	1	
Mode	1	
Std. deviation	19.634	

Source: Primary Data from Field Survey

How did you get to know about mobile banking?

120 responses

Fig 16 How to Know About Mobile Banking

Table-16B shows that there are so many media through which customers are influenced to use mobile banking. 47.5% of respondents are influenced by the internet whereas 22.5% respondent is influenced by friend and 21.7% respondents are influenced by the bank itself. For that reason, we can clearly say that Social influence positively affects behavioral intention to use mobile banking. So, hypothesis 5 is accepted.

Fig 17 Overall customer’s intention towards the adoption of mobile banking
Source: Calculated from Primary Data

The above bar graph shows that the average mean value of the perception statements in the perceived risk dimension is 4.01 on a 5point Likert scale. This means that customers are satisfied with the adoption of mobile banking. Because Mobile banking gives the flexibility to conduct banking business 24hours/day, easy to use, Instructions in the mobile system are clear and understandable, etc.

Table 17 Correlation

Zero-order correlation coefficients for all variables in the study																	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
1.MB gives flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day	---																
2.MB transactions save more time	.59	---															
3.MB makes it easier for me to do my banking	.51	.51	---														
4.MB helps me to know the state of my account faster	.40	.48	.46	---													
5.I find MB cost effective as compare to visiting banks	.25	.23	.27	.23	---												
6.MB makes it easier for me to do my banking.	.51	.51	1	.46	.27	---											
7.Learning to use MB was easy for me	.43	.57	.39	.44	.20	.39	---										
8.Instructions in the MB system are clear and understandable	.43	.39	.29	.31	.18	.29	.62	---									
9.MB has the chance of data loss and fraud	- .08	- .02	- .21	- .06	.03	- .21	.14	- .02	---								
10.MB has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability	- .08	- .18	- .05	- .10	- .08	- .05	- .10	- .11	.18	---							
11.I think that I have received enough information about MB	.36	.43	.46	.29	.22	.46	.48	.58	- .07	- .05	---						
12.I think that using the new MB service is beneficial for me	.46	.33	.50	.41	.29	.50	.39	.46	- .05	- .09	.54	---					
13.MB is compatible to my banking needs	.30	.35	.43	.52	.36	.43	.38	.35	- .05	.06	.36	.37	---				
14.I believe that MB are trustworthy	.27	.30	.39	.27	.33	.39	.36	.47	- .20	.08	.44	.38	.50	---			
15.I find MB cost effective as compare to visiting banks	.25	.23	.27	.23	1	.27	.20	.18	.03	- .08	.22	.29	.36	.33	---		
16.I am comfortable using new technologies like MB	.40	.36	.47	.36	.23	.47	.55	.52	.00	- .10	.42	.45	.40	.54	.23	---	
17.I use all the MB services	.16	.23	.18	.25	.12	.18	.39	.30	.16	- .07	.37	.21	.22	.26	.12	.40	---
18.Please rate your overall satisfaction of using MB services.	.49	.38	.56	.48	.38	.56	.48	.37	- .09	.02	.56	.47	.36	.45	.38	.41	.32

Source: Calculated from primary data

Correlation is a statistical technique that can show whether and how strongly pairs of variables are related. Respondents think that MB transactions save more time have a perfectly positive correlation with MB helps me to know the state of my account faster. That is the reason why customers are satisfied due to checking accounts in a short time. On the other hand, MB makes it easier for me to do my banking has a perfectly positive correlation with MB gives the flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day. That’s why customers are satisfied due to perform their banking within any time.

Respondent also thinks that Learning to use MB was easy for me has a perfectly positive correlation with Instructions in the MB system are clear and understandable I think that I have received enough information about MB. As a result, customers are satisfied because of getting clear learning. They again think that I find MB cost-effective as compare to visiting banks has a perfectly positive correlation with MB has the chance of data loss and fraud. So, after exiting the risk of data loss and fraud, people use mobile banking because of its efficiency.

Respondent thinks that I think that using the new MB service is beneficial for me has a perfectly positive correlation with I find MB cost-effective as compare to visiting banks. So, customers are highly satisfied with mobile banking due to effectiveness and efficiency. They think that I believe that MB is trustworthy has a perfectly negative correlation with MB has the chance of data loss and fraud, MB has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability. So, Customers are more concerned about the adoption of mobile banking.

I should use all mobile banking facilities has a negative correlation with MB has the chance of data loss and fraud, MB has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability, and I think that using the new mobile banking service is beneficial for me. That is the reason why customers are highly concerned with the adoption of mobile banking. Some other respondents think that I should use mobile banking has a positive correlation with mobile banking is compatible with my banking needs. That is why customers are highly satisfied with the adoption of mobile banking.

Mobile banking is compatible with my banking needs has a perfectly positive correlation with mobile banking gives me the flexibility to conduct banking business 24hours/day. Mobile banking is compatible with my banking needs does not affect mobile banking gives the flexibility to conduct banking business 24hours/day.

➤ *Regression Analysis*

Regression analysis is a constructive statistical technique that can be used to analyze the associations between a set of independent variables and a single dependent variable(hair,2005). This equation has the form:

- $Y = b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + A$
- Where,
- Y= The dependent variable
- X1, X2, and so on = The independent Variable
- b1, b2, and so on = The coefficient or multipliers that describe the size of the effect the independent variable has on dependent variable Y
- A= The value Y is predicted to have when all the independent variables are equal to zero

Here I used multiple regressions to study the direct effects of adoption drivers on the intention to use mobile banking services. Because of analyzing the direct relationship between Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, awareness, customer service, overall customer intention, and perceived risk associated with the intention to adopt mobile banking.

Table 18.1 Model Summary Multiple Regression Analysis

Standard Error	0.609
Observations	120

• **Independent Variables**

MB gives the flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day, MB transactions save more time, MB makes it easier for me to do my banking, MB helps me to know the state of my account faster, I find MB cost-effective as compare to visiting banks, MB makes it easier for me to do my banking, Learning to use MB was easy for me, Instructions in the MB system are clear and understandable, MB has the chance of data loss and fraud, MB has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability, I think that I have received enough information about MB, I think that using the new MB service is beneficial for me, MB is compatible to my banking needs, I believe that MB is trustworthy, I find MB cost-effective as compare to visiting banks, I am comfortable using new technologies like MB, I use all the MB services.

• **Dependent Variable**

Overall customer intention towards the adoption of mobile banking.

Table 18.2 ANOVA

ANOVA	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	15	55.424	3.695	9.963	0.000
Residual	104	38.568	0.371		
Total	119	93.992			

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) determines whether the means of three or more groups are different. For testing equality, ANOVA uses F-tests.

Table 17(a) and (b) represent that, the F-statistics for this study is significant at 1 Percent level (sig. $F < 0.1$) which represents the fitness of the model. Here I found that the total standard error is 0.609 and total observation is 120. In regression periods degree of freedom is 15, the sum of a square is 55.424, the mean of a square is 3.695 and F is 9.963. On the other hand, in residual periods degree of freedom is 104, the sum of the square is 38.568, mean of the square is 0.371 of the intentions can be explained by Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, awareness, customer service, overall customer intension and perceived of risk.

Table 18.3 Coefficients

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	-0.509	0.545	-0.935	0.352	-1.589	0.571	-1.589	0.571
Mobile banking gives flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day.	0.265	0.100	2.638	0.010	0.066	0.464	0.066	0.464
Mobile banking transactions save more time.	-0.267	0.125	-2.130	0.036	-0.516	-0.018	-0.516	-0.018
Mobile banking helps me to know the state of my account faster.	0.240	0.084	2.852	0.005	0.073	0.407	0.073	0.407
I find mobile banking cost effective as compare to visiting banks.	0.139	0.055	2.533	0.013	0.030	0.248	0.030	0.248
Mobile banking makes it easier for me to do my banking.	0.231	0.102	2.266	0.026	0.029	0.434	0.029	0.434
Learning to use Mobile banking was easy for me.	0.267	0.110	2.419	0.017	0.048	0.486	0.048	0.486
Instructions in the Mobile banking system are clear and understandable.	-0.153	0.096	-1.598	0.113	-0.344	0.037	-0.344	0.037
Mobile banking has the chance of data loss and fraud.	-0.024	0.054	-0.449	0.654	-0.132	0.083	-0.132	0.083
MB has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability.	0.087	0.058	1.491	0.139	-0.029	0.202	-0.029	0.202
I think that I have received enough information about MB.	0.298	0.086	3.449	0.001	0.126	0.469	0.126	0.469
I think that using the new MB service is beneficial for me.	-0.012	0.080	-0.144	0.886	-0.170	0.147	-0.170	0.147
Mobile banking is compatible to my banking needs.	-0.135	0.079	-1.702	0.092	-0.292	0.022	-0.292	0.022
I believe that mobile banking is trustworthy.	0.185	0.085	2.175	0.032	0.016	0.354	0.016	0.354
I am comfortable using new technologies like mobile banking.	-0.077	0.089	-0.862	0.391	-0.254	0.100	-0.254	0.100
I use all the mobile banking services.	0.046	0.048	0.965	0.337	-0.049	0.141	-0.049	0.141

Source: Collected from primary data

From the above coefficient analysis, we found that the intercept of the coefficient in the regression equation is -0.509. Mobile banking gives the flexibility to conduct Banking business 24hours/day, Mobile banking helps me to know the state of my account faster, Mobile banking transactions save more time, I find mobile banking cost-effective as compare to visiting banks, Mobile banking makes it easier for me to do my banking, Learning to use Mobile banking was easy for me, MB has inadequate information on the website and less operational reliability, I think that I have received enough information about MB, I believe that mobile banking is trustworthy, I use all the mobile banking services has a positive correlation with the Overall customer intension towards the adoption of mobile banking. It indicates that as the value of this independent variable increases, the mean of the dependent variable which is Overall customer intention towards the adoption of mobile banking also tends to increase and vice

versa.

On the other hand, Mobile banking transactions save more time, Instructions in the Mobile banking system are clear and understandable, Mobile banking has the chance of data loss and fraud, I think that using the new MB service is beneficial for me, Mobile banking is compatible to my banking needs, I am comfortable using new technologies like mobile banking has a negative Correlation with the Overall customer intension towards the adoption of mobile banking. It indicates that as the value of this independent variable increases, the mean of the Overall customer intention towards the adoption of mobile banking tends to decrease and vice versa.

CHAPTER SIX RECOMMENDATION

➤ *Recommendation*

The result of this study illustrated that there is a perfectly negative correlation between the Usage of mobile banking services and perceived risk. So, it is necessary to expand the focus on the effect of usage on perceived risk. As a result, it will be easy to find the reasons why respondents who use mobile banking services do not want to face perceived risk. On the other hand, there is also a negative relationship between Customer trust and perceived risk. Building customer awareness about mobile banking usages is required to eliminate the perceived risk. Customers should regularly check transaction details that are using so that there will be no chance for unauthorized transactions. Customers should apply a difficult password and change it frequently. Banks need to operate mobile banking software for tracking unauthorized access.

Telecommunication department and cellular service providers should extend their network coverage in rural and remote areas to facilitate communication and m-banking also. The government should establish conditional financial support for proper cellular service providers to extend such networks in rural areas. The banks should enhance their refund facilities' concerns if wrong transactions are made by customers by mistake or if any.

Finally, in order to expand mobile banking adoption intention, banks have to build favourable attitude through enhanced perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived innovation, consumer awareness as well as perceived risks associated.

CHAPTER SEVEN CONCLUSION

➤ *Conclusion*

Mobile banking is a new technological invention in the banking sector of Bangladesh. Mobile banking lets the world enter a new area. This study is based on the various risks and benefits of mobile banking. There are so many inactive subscribers who have an account but do not use it for transaction purposes because of the effect of the factors of adopting mobile banking. Among these factors, perceived risk is the main concern because people who are using mobile banking services are not interested to face perceived risk. They want the actual benefits of mobile banking for making their life easy and comfortable. People are more concerned about their security while using mobile banking. Customers will never compromise their security. So, service innovators need to provide the best benefit to the customers as well as ignoring the perceived risk. There is also a requirement to generate mass-awareness about mobile banking so that more and more people use it for their benefit. Over the last few years, mobile telephone service extended tremendously and it provides golden opportunities to extend m-banking service in Bangladesh. The findings of this study revealed that in Bangladesh the perceived usefulness, subjective norm, perceived ease of use, perceived credibility, consumer awareness, and perceived risks about mobile banking were the factors affecting the behavioral motivation of mobile users to adopt mobile banking services. However, mobile banking customers are increasing because it is comfortable with the digital lifestyle in Bangladesh.

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